

ENGINEERING TIME: INVENTING THE QUARTZ WRISTWATCH

*Carlene E. Stephens, National Museum of American History,
Smithsonian Institution, Washington, DC*

Introduction

Clocks and watches stand at an important crossroads where science, technology and society intersect. Changes in timekeeping technology, beginning with the invention of the mechanical clock around A.D. 1300, have influenced the character of scientific observation, aided the development of other machine technologies and brought significant revisions to the way people think about and behave in time.

One of the most recent episodes in this long history is the invention of the electronic wristwatch. What follows here is a brief summary of a larger work in progress. This preview introduces the engineers who completely reinvented the wristwatch with all new electronic components thirty years ago, considers the contexts in which they worked, and analyzes consumer reception, especially the lively public debate over the comparative benefits of digital versus analog watch displays.

The history of the electronic watch is worth a closer look. Its development during the 1960s was in the vanguard of a dramatic shift from a mechanical to an electronic world. The wristwatch was one of the first consumer products to make the transition, just as, at the beginning of the nineteenth century, clocks were among the first consumer products made in factories by machine.

The Earliest Electronic Watches

In 1960 the watchmaking firm Bulova introduced a new kind of watch. Bulova electrical engineer Max Hetzel had designed a watch that substituted a metal tuning fork for the traditional watch balance wheel, the first innovation in the watch's oscillator since it was introduced sometime in the 15th century. The result was the most accurate wristwatch then available.

The Accutron was a powerful catalyst. Simultaneously in Japan, Switzerland and the United States three independent development teams, consisting of university-trained mechanical and electrical engineers, sought alternatives to the Accutron's new precision. In the end, they found themselves experimenting with newly available electronics components.

In Japan, Suwa Seikosha (now Seiko Epson) began to explore the possibility of an electronic watch before any of its competitors. The firm organized a team of mechanical engineers in 1959 under Tsuneya Nakamura to investigate

quartz timekeepers. Their first watch, the first quartz watch sold anywhere in the world, was the Seiko Astron SQ. It went on sale in Tokyo on Christmas Day 1969.

A consortium of Swiss watch companies established a new electronics research laboratory in the early 1960s. At CEH (Centre Electronique Horloger) in Neuchâtel, work began on a series of quartz watch prototypes, which won international time trials in 1967. The Swiss project leader was Max Forrer, a physicist trained at Stanford University. In 1970 watches containing the Beta 21 electronic module went on sale under the brand names of sixteen different Swiss watch companies.

In 1967, the year the Swiss tested their prototypes, the Hamilton Watch Co. of Lancaster, Pa., had ten years experience making an electromechanical watch powered by a battery and had begun to develop a quartz watch. To stay competitive Hamilton changed direction and, under electrical engineer John Bergey, began work on what would be the world's first digital electronic watch. Instead of a dial and hands, the Pulsar, first sold in 1972, provided time on demand with flashing red LED numerals.

Marketing to Men

Hamilton needed to create a market and an identity for the very unusual Pulsar. The firm targeted male buyers and placed the Pulsar squarely in the category of space-age technology. The Pulsar, claimed Hamilton advertising, was no ordinary watch. It was a "wrist computer" based on the most up-to-the-minute know-how. Its very name came from outer space, from the stars that emit radio waves at regular intervals.

Hamilton also understood that watches are fashion items. The high costs of production ensured that the Pulsar would be marketed as a luxury item. Designers created expensive gold and stainless steel cases for the first Pulsars, which were sold only through high-end jewelers.

Sales really took off when James Bond (the Roger Moore version) wore little more than a Pulsar in a love scene in the 1973 film *Live and Let Die*. Celebrities and politicians sported Pulsars too. The watch quickly earned the reputation as the fashion item of choice for rich and powerful men.

Hamilton's success tempted both traditional watch firms and upstart electronics companies to jump into the market with their own products. By the mid-1970s about forty American companies were mass-producing electronic watches. Prices plunged. Just four years after the costly

Pulsar appeared, consumers could purchase a digital watch from Texas Instruments for only \$20. Cheap digital watches poured by the millions out of U.S. and Asian factories. The power-hungry flashing red numerals of the LED gave way to a whole new display technology—liquid crystal displays. By the late 1970s LCDs were more popular than LEDs. These cheap digital watches gave just about everyone access to the split-second accuracy once available to only scientists and technicians.

Digital vs. Analog

This tidal wave of electronic watches provoked a lively public debate over the comparative benefits of digital versus analog displays.

Consumers lined up on both sides of the debate. During the first few years of digital watches, the novelty attracted real enthusiasts. To many of these “early adopters” time displayed in digits signaled a much more accurate, objective and abstract “scientific” time. But as digital watches flooded the marketplace in the mid-1970s, and smaller models for women and children became available, public complaints began to mount.

Some consumer complaints, which at first glance seemed to be about the drawbacks of reading time displayed in digits, actually had to do with the poor quality and design of these cheap timekeepers. LEDs couldn’t be read in sunlight. LCDs were invisible at night. Batteries were annoyingly short-lived. Setting the new watches was always complicated, often required extra tools, and sometimes seemed next to impossible. Cheap watches could be unreliable. Buyers returned malfunctioning watches to their manufacturers in record numbers. And many found the digital display and the plastic watches downright ugly. Manufacturers heard these complaints and made appropriate changes, giving consumers a huge role in shaping the final form and function of quartz watches.

But consumer concerns went beyond dreadful quality and design. Some began to question the very nature of digital time itself. For some adults, the transition to digital proved genuinely difficult. Their knowledge of time was rooted in the analog dial, disrupted by abstract numbers without the familiar context of hands rotating in a circle.

A frequent complaint was that digitals showed only a given moment in time, only incomplete information. Others criticized the digital display because it was too precise. And some parents and teachers worried that children would lose the ability to tell time by the traditional clock.

The public discussion reveals passionate opinions about how time on clocks or watches is represented. But it fails to reveal precisely why people were concerned. What exactly would people have lost if the analog dial disappeared forever? And were the complaints informed or merely frustrations vented in the face of unwanted change?

It seemed not to matter to the opponents that digital representations of time were not new when digital watches came on the scene in the 1970s. Printed schedules for trains, or radio and TV program listings showed time represented numerically—that is, the hour followed by a colon and then minutes. Public clocks displaying digital time, especially the time and temperature signs commonly found on banks, had been introduced in the 1950s.

What seemed to matter more was that the digital watch display coincided in the 1970s with proposed—and to some alarming—changes in other deeply entrenched numerical standards and practices. Many were distressed about pocket calculators and efforts to convert the United States to the metric system.

Digital watches grabbed public attention in the 1970s because the new electronic technology made digital time cheap, ubiquitous, portable, and personal, leading many consumers to fear that digital watches would make the analog dial extinct.

In fact, this fear turned out to be unwarranted. Since about the mid 1980s, people have bought more watches with analog dials than with digital displays. Digital watches have not disappeared, of course. They have come to occupy lucrative niche markets, where they fill the needs of those who in their everyday life care about fractions of seconds, or use the timers and alarms that these multifunction watches can provide.

References

1. David Landes, *Revolution in Time: Clocks and the Making of the Modern World*, Cambridge, MA, 1983.
2. Bob Johnstone, *We Were Burning: Japanese Entrepreneurs and the Forging of the Electronic Age*, Boulder, CO and Oxford, 1999.
3. Pieter Doensen, *Watch: History of Modern Wristwatch Design*, Ghent, 1994.
4. Stephens, Carlene and Maggie Dennis, “Engineering Time: Inventing the Quartz Wristwatch.” *British Journal for the History of Science* 33(2000): 477-497.
5. Maggie Dennis, “Wrist Computer and Babe Magnet: Masculinity and the Origins of the Digital Watch” (paper presented at the annual meeting of the Society for the History of Technology, Munich, Germany, August 2000).
6. Maggie Dennis and Carlene Stephens, “Giving Time a New Face: Digital Watch Displays and Changing Perceptions of Time” (paper presented at the annual meeting of the American Historical Association, Boston, Mass., January 2001).